

Ethnomedicinal Plants Used by The Folklore of Gorakhpur District, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract

From the beginning of human existence, societies relied on plants and their products for treating various diseases. In some areas, these traditional remedies have been endemic and have been passed down orally over centuries. They do not exist in written form. The present study was undertaken to document the ethnobotanical knowledge of medicinal plants in Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, by engaging with local herbalists, elderly individuals, and other knowledgeable community members.

The field survey was carried out at different villages of Gorakhpur. The informants were interviewed about the plants having ethnomedicinal values through discussions. A total of 83 ethnomedicinal plant species belonging to 45 families were reported to treat various ailments. The most frequently utilized plant part was the leaf followed by the root. The whole plant was also utilized in some cases.

The ethnomedicinal plants used by the folklore of Gorakhpur district were tabulated and their families arranged alphabetically followed by botanical name, local name, plant part used, habit, and ethnomedicinal uses.

Keywords

Ethnomedicinal Plants, Medicinal plants, Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh.

Introduction

A famous quote by Norwegian Artist Edvard Munch "*Nature is not all that is visible... also includes the inner pictures of the soul*" speaks many things about the mother "Nature" and her creation. Nature is enormous in its resources which not only provide food, clothes, and shelter but also provide medicine from the beginning of mankind. Out of these resources, the greatest gift of nature is her atmosphere with food and medicine. Plants are one of the important sources of medicines, which not only help mankind to sustain but also to grow, develop, and live, particularly from diseases, suffering, and discomfort. Scientifically, "Ethnomedicine" is the study of "folk medicine" of ethnic groups, their wisdom and methods are transmitted orally over centuries but they are not found in written forms. (Chattopadhyay, 2009, 2010). The native people of India to date used their medication which might be more appropriately defined as the use of plants in the treatment of diseases and should be more accurately termed "Ethnobotanical medicine" (Fabricant and Farnsworth, 2001).

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to study the ethnomedicinal plants used by the folklore of Gorakhpur District of Uttar Pradesh.

Review of Literature

A good ample of natural medicine comes from forest species. For the remedies, few plants are cultivated while most of them are present in the form of weeds. There are various modes of administration like decoction, paste, juice, tincture, and powders. Different parts of the plants or sometimes whole plants are used in the treatment of the diseases.

Over the past year, several papers have been published on the ethnomedicinal plants. A review of the literature discloses that the medicinal flora in India is quite rich, and the tribal and rural population still depends on herbal medicine for their treatments. The information should be compiled before it is lost as the folkloristics are depleting day by day due to increased urbanization.

Gorakhpur flora has been assembled as flora gorakhpurensis by T.N. Srivastava in 1976. V. K. Singh, Zaheer Anwar Ali & M.K. Siddiqui (1997) studied the medicinal plants used by the forest ethnics of Gorakhpur District, Uttar Pradesh, India. Ravi Pratap Gautam, S. Dominic Rajkumar, S.K. Srivastava and S. K. Singh studied the various folk uses of plants from Kusmi Forest, Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh. Manisha Mishra, Deepa Srivastava (2024) studied the native uses of medicinal flora of Gorakhpur. Therefore, the present work has been carried out to

enumerate and document the ethnomedicinal plants used by the folklore of the Gorakhpur district.

Methodology

Study Area

The present study focuses on the Gorakhpur district, situated within the Terai belt of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India.

Geographically, the district lies between latitudes 26°5' N–27°29' N and longitudes 83°4'E-84°26 E with a land area of 34,83.8 km². Geomorphologically, the terai landscape is characterized by a relatively uniform topography and highly fertile alluvial soils resulting from fluvial deposition by the Rapti and Ghaghra rivers. Forests are dominated by species such as *Shorea robusta* (Sal) and *Tectona grandis* (Teak). Additionally, the landscape includes grasslands and riparian ecosystems that support biotic communities.

Map 1. Map of the study area

Medicinal Plant Survey and Data Collection

A detailed extensive ethnobotanical survey was conducted in villages of the Gorakhpur district during the months September 2024 to March 2025 to systematically document knowledge related to ethnomedicinal plants. Information was collected through direct engagement with local people through interviews and group discussions.

Emphasis was placed on gathering information from traditional healers, elderly individuals, and other knowledgeable residents to record the indigenous use of plant species as medicine. All the discussions were done with the people in Hindi language for their comfort. The information gathered includes common diseases cured by plants, local names of plants, habits, plant parts used, and ethnomedicinal uses. The finalized list of the plants was compiled following the International Plant Names Index (<http://www.ipni.org>) and Tropicos. The data collected was presented in tabular form.

Result and Discussion

In the course of this survey, 107 plants were identified. Out of these 83 are used in native medicines (Table 1).

Fig.1 Some Important Families of Ethnomedicinal Plants

Description of Medicinal Plant Families

These 83 plant species belong to 45 different families. The most frequent families (Fig. 1) are Amaranthaceae (7 species), Fabaceae (6 species), Euphorbiaceae (5 species), Solanaceae (4 species), Asteraceae (4 species), Malvaceae (4 species), Moraceae (3 species),

Apocynaceae (3 species), Acanthaceae (3 species), Rutaceae (2 species), Poaceae (2 species), Nyctaginaceae (2 species), Myrtaceae (2 species), Combretaceae (2 species), Asclepiadaceae (2 species), Liliaceae (2 species), Lamiaceae (2 species).

The rest of the families (Verbenaceae, Vitaceae, Mimosaceae, Annonaceae, Papaveraceae, Linaceae, Menispermaceae, Meliaceae, Caesalpiniaceae, Bombaceae, Cannabinaceae, Musaceae, Capparaceae, Commelinaceae, Tiliaceae, Zingiberaceae, Cyperaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Fumariaceae, Sapotaceae, Anacardiaceae, Moringaceae, Oxalidaceae, Piperaceae, Plumbaginaceae, Brassicaceae, Polygonaceae,) are represented with single plant species.

Plant Parts Used

Local peoples utilized different parts of plants (in combination or separately) in the study area for the treatment of various human diseases. Leaves were the most used (44.57%) plant part, followed by roots (34.93%), whole plant (10.84%), fruits (7.2%), bark (4.81%), seeds (3.61%), flower (2.40%), rhizome (2.40%), stem (1.20%), latex (1.20%) (Fig. 2). There are plant's soft parts such as leaves, buds, and flowers. The soft parts of the plants are rich in volatile components, fragrances, and active principles.

Fig. 2 Percentage Contribution of Plant Parts used of Ethnomedicinal Plant

Ethnomedicinal Plant Enumerations

Numerous growth forms were used as medicinal plants (Fig. 3). The contribution of herbs was the highest (49.39%) followed by trees (28.91%), shrubs (15.66%), and climbers (6.02%). The finding supports the widely reported pattern of herbaceous species being the dominant life form in medicinal plant assemblages across various ethnobotanical studies in India and other countries. This predominance of herbs in the medicinal flora may be attributed to their greater accessibility in the local habitats compared to shrubs, and trees.

Fig. 3 Percentage Contribution of several Life-Forms of Ethnomedicinal Plants

Mode of Preparation, Administration, and Application

The mode of preparation of the remedies of 83 plant species are classified according to their type of preparation, which disclosed that decoction/tea (31 species) was a widely used preparation method by local peoples, followed by paste (20 species), juice/extract (18 species), crushed (9 species), powdered/grinded (08 species), roasted/cooked (04 species), directly eaten (03 species) and chewed (01 species) (Fig. 4). It also shows that the remedies of ethnomedicinal plants, used both externally and internally by the local peoples.

Fig. 4 Commonly used techniques in the preparation of plant remedies

These ethnomedicinal plants are broadly used by local peoples to treat various diseases like weakness, dysentery, cold and cough, headache, cuts and wounds, fever, kidney stones, malaria, asthma, diarrhea, jaundice, pain, typhoid, cancer, skin diseases, piles, blood pressure, anemia, heart disease, diabetes, rheumatism, epilepsy, bronchitis, boils, intake of toxic substances, bone fracture, snake bite, constipation, inflammation, urinary trouble, chicken pox, back pain, reproductive problems etc.

Vaids also uses these plants for different compositions. Although these plants need to be conserved, the entire forest is getting depleted due to increased human activities and industrialization.

Conclusion

The study provides information about the folk knowledge of medicinal plants used by local peoples of Gorakhpur district, Uttar Pradesh, India. In primary health care, people of rural areas of this region still have good knowledge of medicinal plants. But this knowledge is decreasing day by day with the increase in education. In the interview, we found that in recent years, people have started to rely more on Western medicine than folk medicine. If not documented the ethnomedicinal knowledge of the region may be forever lost. Therefore, there is an urgent need to compile information before it is lost, as folkloristics are depleting day by day due to the influence of Western medicine and increased urbanization.

Table 1. List of Ethnomedicinal Plants Used by The Folklore of Gorakhpur District, Uttar Pradesh

FAMILY AND BOTANICAL NAME OF THE PLANTS	LOCAL NAME	PLANT PART USED	HABIT	ETHNOMEDICINAL USES
Acanthaceae				
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i> Nees.	Adusa	Leaf	Shrub	Fresh leaves decoction is given in the treatment of colds and asthma.
<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Nees.	Kalmegh	Leaf	Herb	Decoction of leaves is given for treating the common cold and fever.
<i>Hygrophila spinosa</i> Schumacher.	Tal makhana	Leaf, Root	Herb	Root extract is used in the treatment of rheumatism, jaundice, and body pain. Leaf is used as a diuretic.
Amaranthaceae				
<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Latjeera	Root	Shrub	A paste of root is applied at the place of the Scorpion sting.
<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.) Juss.	Gedua ki chal	Root	Herb	A paste of root is rubbed on the forehead to relieve headaches.
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br. Ex DC.	Gurra bhaji	Whole plant	Herb	Crushed whole plant and mixed with one teaspoon honey and is given for the treatment of diarrhea. Whole plant paste is also used for skin problems.
<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Kateeli chaulai	Root	Herb	Fresh roots of the plants are grounded and applied externally to the point of snake bite.
<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	Chaulai	Leaf	Herb	Fresh leaves are cooked and given in the treatment of hemorrhoids.
<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	Murdha	Leaf	Herb	Fresh leaves of the plants are crushed and given for the purification of blood.
<i>Gomphrena celosioides</i> Mart.	Kassia	Whole plant	Herb	Decoction of the whole plant is given in urinary trouble.

Anacardiaceae				
<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Aam	Leaf	Tree	The young leaves of the plant are grounded and given to cure dysentery and diarrhea.
Annonaceae				
<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Sharifa	Leaf, Seed, Fruit	Tree	Seeds are dried and powdered used to get rid of lice, and Leaf extract is used to treat ulcers and sores. Fruit is used as a sedative.
Apocynaceae				
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i> (L.) G. Don	Sadabahar	Leaf, Root	Herb	Decoction of leaves is given in the treatment of malaria. Roots are used to regulate blood sugar levels.
<i>Nerium indicum</i> Mill.	Kaner	Root	Tree	The roots are dried, ground, and fried in the ghee to cure ear inflammation.
<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i> (L.) Benth. ex Kurz	Sargandha	Leaf	Shrub	Leaf paste is given in the treatment of fever.
Asclepiadaceae				
<i>Calotropis procera</i> (L.) W. T. Aiton	Madar	Leaf	Shrub	Fresh leaves are warmed and applied to the wounded area.
<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) R. Br.	Anantamul	Leaf	Climber	Leaf paste is given for treating skin disease (leukoderma).
Asteraceae				
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	Bhangra	Leaf	Herb	The leaf is crushed and applied to heal the wound.
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> L.	Bhringraj	Leaf	Herb	Leaf paste is applied externally to cure skin diseases. Leaf is boiled with mustard oil and applied to the scalp for hair loss.
<i>Launaea procumbens</i> Roxb.	Jangali gobhi	Root	Herb	Extract of fresh root mixed with honey is taken for treating dysentery.
<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	Phulana	Leaf	Herb	Juice of leaves is applied externally on the cuts and wounds.
Bombaceae				
<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L.	Semal	Root	Tree	Young roots are dried and powdered and are taken with milk early morning to treat sexual impotency.
Brassicaceae				
<i>Raphanus sativus</i> L.	Muli	Root	Herb	Juice of root is given in urinary trouble.
Caesalpiniaceae				
<i>Bauhinia variegata</i> (L.) Benth.	Kachnar	Root	Tree	Decoction of root is given to reduce obesity.
Cannabaceae				
<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.	Bhang	Leaf, fruit	Shrub	The paste of the leaf is mixed with turmeric and applied to treat wounds. Seed is used to relieve joint pain.
Capparaceae				
<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Hurhura	Leaf	Herb	Leaves are boiled and mixed with ghee and applied externally to heal the cuts.
Combretaceae				
<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb.) Wight & Arn.	Arjun	Bark	Tree	The decoction of the bark is used to treat heart failure, angina pain, and hypertension.
<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.	Harra	Fruit	Tree	The paste of fruit is used in healing ulcers and wounds.
Commelinaceae				
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Kankaua	Seed	Herb	Decoction of seed is given to treat dysentery and diarrhea.
Cucurbitaceae				
<i>Diplocyclos palmatus</i> (L.) C. Jeffrey	Kawabel	Leaf	Climber	Juice of leaves is given for the treatment of diabetes and also in skin diseases.
Cyperaceae				
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Motha	Rhizome	Herb	Decoction of the rhizome is used in the treatment of dysentery, nausea, and malaria and it also regulates menstruation.
Euphorbiaceae				
<i>Emblica officinalis</i> Gaertn.	Amla	Fruit, leaf	Tree	Fruit extract is used in diabetes and cancer. Leaf extract is given to reduce inflammation.
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Dudhi	Whole plant	Herb	Whole plant juice is used to treat conjunctivitis.
<i>Mallotus philippensis</i> (Lam.) Muell. Arg.	Sindure	Fruit	Tree	Fruit paste is applied externally to treat ringworm.
<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> L.	Bhumi amla	Whole plant	Herb	Whole plant decoction is given for treating kidney and gallbladder stones and jaundice.
<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Arandi	Leaf	Shrub	Leaf paste is applied to relieve muscle pain and soreness.
Fabaceae				
<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (L.) P.J.H. Hurter & Mabb.	Babool	Bark	Tree	Decoction of the bark is used in the treatment of hemorrhoids.
<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	Palash	Bark, Leaf	Tree	The juice of stem bark is used treatment of goiter and is also used as a disinfectant. Leaf paste is applied externally to the point of snake bite.
<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Amaltas	Seed	Tree	The decoction of seeds is used to treat gastritis and improve appetite.
<i>Delonix regia</i> (Boj. Ex Hook) Raf.	Gulmohar	Flower, Leaf	Tree	The juice of flowers is used in the treatment of diarrhea. The leaves are used in rheumatism, arthritis, and inflammation.
<i>Desmodium triflorum</i> (L.) DC.	Tinpatia	Leaf	Herb	The leaf juice is given for the treatment of diarrhoea and dysentery.
<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L.	Chhui mui	Leaf	Herb	Leaf decoction is used in the treatment of diarrhea and hemorrhoids.

<u>Fumariaceae</u>				
<i>Fumaria indica</i> L.	Pitpapra	Whole plant	Herb	The decoction of whole plant is given to purify blood in skin diseases.
<u>Lamiaceae</u>				
<i>Leucas aspera</i> (willd.) Link.	Guma	Leaf	Herb	The decoction of leaves is given in the treatment of fever.
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> L.	Tulsi	Root	Herb	The decoction of the root is used to treat constipation, lack of appetite, and malaria.
<u>Liliaceae</u>				
<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Satawar	Root	Shrub	Root powder with milk is given to increase milk production in nursing mothers.
<i>Glottosa superba</i> L.	Kalihari	Root	Shrub	Decoction of root with sesame oil is applied to relieve in joint pain.
<u>Linaceae</u>				
<i>Linum usitatissimum</i> L.	Teesi	Seeds	Herb	Seed paste mixed with oil and applied externally on abscesses, wounds, ulcers.
<u>Malvaceae</u>				
<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet.	Kanghi	Leaf, Root	Shrub	The leaf juice is used to heal the boils and wounds. Crushed root with milk is given to combat fatigue.
<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm. f.	Baraira	Whole plant	Herb	The leaf paste is applied externally to heal the wound. Decoction of the root is used in the treatment of fever.
<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L.	Bariyar	Root	Herb	Root extract is given for treating constipation.
<i>Urena lobata</i> L.	Kathua	Root	Herb	Decoction of the root is used in the treatment of joint pains.
<u>Meliaceae</u>				
<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juzz.	Neem	Bark, Leaf	Tree	Decoction of bark is given to treat malaria. The decoction of leaves is used to wash the wounds and its paste is applied to treat ulcers, and abscesses.
<u>Menispermaceae</u>				
<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Thunb.) Miers.	Giloy	Leaf	Climber	Leaf extract is given to treat fever and maintain blood sugar levels.
<u>Mimosaceae</u>				
<i>Albizia lebbek</i> Benth.	Siris	Root	Shrub	Root paste is applied at the point of snake bite.
<u>Moraceae</u>				
<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Bargad	Latex	Tree	The latex is applied to treat the sores and wounds. Also used to expel the thorns broken inside the body.
<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Peepal	Root	Tree	Root mixed with sugar is given in chicken pox.
<i>Morus alba</i> L.	Shaltoot	Root	Tree	Decoction of root is given for treating blood in cough and fever.
<u>Moringaceae</u>				
<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Sehjan	Leaf	Tree	Leaves decoction is used to reduce inflammation. Leaf paste is applied externally to cure wounds and cuts.
<u>Musaceae</u>				
<i>Musa paradisiaca</i> L.	Kela	Root	Herb	Root mixed with saffron is given early morning to treat enteric fever.
<u>Myrtaceae</u>				
<i>Eucalyptus citriodora</i> Hook.	Safeda	Leaf	Tree	The decoction of leaves is used to treat fever, common cold, and sore throat.
<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Jamun	Bark, Seeds	Tree	Decoction of bark is used to reduce inflammation. The seeds are dried and powdered and given in diabetes.
<u>Nyctaginaceae</u>				
<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> L. nom. Cons.	Punarnava	Whole plant	Herb	Decoction of the whole plant is given in kidney stones.
<i>Mirabilis jalapa</i> L.	Gulabans	Root	Shrub	Root paste is applied externally to treat boils and wounds.
<u>Oxalidaceae</u>				
<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Khatti buti	Leaf	Herb	The leaves are crushed and applied to cuts to stop bleeding.
<u>Papaveraceae</u>				
<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Bharbhar	Root	Herb	Root paste is used as an antidote for snake bites.
<u>Piperaceae</u>				
<i>Piper longum</i> L.	Pipali	Root	Climber	Decoction of root is used to treat bronchitis, common cold, and asthma.
<u>Plumbaginaceae</u>				
<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.	Chitrak	Root	Herb	Crushed root with oil is given in the treatment of scabies and ear pain.
<u>Poaceae</u>				
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Doob ghas	Whole plant	Herb	Whole plant juice is given in the treatment of dysentery.
<i>Desmostachya bipinnata</i> Stapf.	Dhab	Root	Herb	A root infusion is given for treating urinary trouble.
<u>Polygonaceae</u>				
<i>Rumex dentatus</i> L.	Ambavati	Leaf	Herb	Leaf extract is given in the intake of poisonous substances.
<u>Rutaceae</u>				
<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Correa	Bel	Fruit, Leaf	Tree	Crushed fruit is given in diarrhea and dysentery. Leaf juice is given for treating jaundice.
<i>Murraya koenigii</i> (L.)	Katnim	Leaf	Tree	The decoction of leaves is taken in nausea and fever.
<u>Sapotaceae</u>				
<i>Madhuca indica</i> Gmel.	Mahua	Root	Tree	Root paste is given to expel intestinal worms.

<u>Scrophulariaceae</u>				
<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.) pennell	Brahmi	Whole plant	Herb	Decoction of whole plant is taken to treat fever.
<u>Solanaceae</u>				
<i>Physalis minima</i> L.	Rasbhari	Fruit	Herb	Fruits are cooked and given to treat constipation.
<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	Makoi	Root	Herb	The decoction of the root is given in the treatment of common cold and fever.
<i>Solanum surattense</i> Burm.f	Bhat kattiya	Leaf	Herb	The decoction of leaves is used in the treatment of cough and hemorrhoids.
<i>Withania somnifera</i> (L.) Dunal.	Ashwagandha	Leaf	Shrub	The fresh leaves are chewed on an empty stomach to reduce obesity.
<u>Tiliaceae</u>				
<i>Grewia asiatica</i> L.	Phalsa	Root	Tree	The paste of root is applied externally to treat the joint and body pain.
<u>Verbenaceae</u>				
<i>Vitex negundo</i> L.	Nishindi	Leaf	Shrub	The decoction of leaves is given to get rid of helminths in children.
<u>Vitaceae</u>				
<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> L.	Hadjod	Root, Stem	Climber	The root and stem paste are applied for the treatment of bone fractures.
<u>Zingiberaceae</u>				
<i>Curcuma domestica</i> Val.	Haldi	Rhizome	Herb	The rhizome pastes mixed and boiled with mustard oil are applied externally to treat the injury. Milk with turmeric is also given to cure the common cold.

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